

Innovation of avocado (*Persea americana* Mill.) leaf extract patch for diabetic wound treatment: an in silico and in vivo investigation

Citra Ariani Edityaningrum¹, Najma Annuria Fithri², Laela Hayu Nurani¹, Wahyu Widyaningsih¹, Baiq Shanaya Zaelifa¹, Fivdah Khoeruliani Tazqiyah¹, Revi Adelia¹, Cintana Violena Alifia Putri¹, Daffa Danurwenda¹, Farah Daffa Azzahra², Siti Humairoh², Rumiya Dwi Nindi Marrisca²

¹ Faculty of Pharmacy, Ahmad Dahlan University, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

² Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Sriwijaya University, Indralaya, Indonesia

Corresponding author: Najma Annuria Fithri (najma.fithri@mipa.unsri.ac.id)

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Abstract

Diabetic wounds occur due to blood vessel disorders and prolonged infection, often leading to amputation if left untreated. The wound healing process can be expedited by shortening the inflammation period, thus mitigating infection and promoting proliferation. Avocado leaves (*Persea americana* Mill.) are excellent sources of bioactive compounds, such as tannins, alkaloids, and flavonoids, which are potentially beneficial for wound healing. One of the most ideal delivery systems for the wound healing process is a topical drug delivery system, such as patches, which can be attached to the skin and maintain continuous contact with wounded areas. Various HPMC-based patch formulations were developed and tested for physical properties, weight uniformity, pH, patch thickness, and folding endurance tests. The best-performing patch (F2, with 10% extract) had good weight uniformity (CV 1.29%), pH 5.73 ± 0.04 , thickness 0.62 ± 0.03 mm, and folding endurance 336.6 ± 4.41 times. Prior to *in vivo* testing, an *in silico* test was performed on phytochemicals present in avocado leaves. It was found that caffeic acid and gallic acid present the best binding affinity towards several receptors, namely MMP9, AKT1, and the EGFR pathway, which is critical in angiogenesis and involved in the wound healing process. After obtaining previous *in silico* and optimum formula results, further testing was conducted on experimental animals to determine the efficacy as a diabetic wound healer by observing wound drying, scab formation, and tissue regeneration. Observations conducted over a 14-day period showed that efficacy testing in diabetic mice resulted in a reduction in wound size from 5 mm to approximately ± 1 mm. This activity did not show a statistically significant difference compared to the Bioplacenta positive control under the same testing conditions, indicating a potential beneficial effect of the ALEE patch formulation on the wound healing process.

Keywords

avocado leaf ethanol extract, diabetic wound, formula optimization, HPMC-based patch, *in silico* molecular docking

Introduction

Chronic diseases, including diabetes, are health problems associated with symptoms or disabilities requiring long-term management (Arroyave et al. 2020). The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that the number of people with diabetes mellitus will increase two to three times by 2030, from 8.4 million to 21.3 million (Saedi et al. 2019). Diabetic wounds occur due to nerve and blood vessel disorders, as well as infection. Improper treatment of infection continues to cause rot in the wound and leads to amputation (Farzamfar et al. 2013; Weledji and Fokam 2014). In addition, Indonesia possesses different plants, such as avocado (*Persea americana* Mill.) leaves, used as an alternative to treat diseases. Based on the report by Castro-Lopez et al. (2019), ethanol extract of avocado leaf contains saponin, tannin, alkaloid, and flavonoid compounds. These various phytochemical compounds act as anti-inflammatory and antioxidant compounds, which shorten the inflammation period (Wijaya et al. 2020). Furthermore, flavonoids and tannins have strong potential use for wound healing by increasing collagen production during the proliferation stage (Galicka and Nazaruk 2007).

Several dosage forms are available for wound treatment commercially, including ointments, gels, solutions, and creams (Vicente-da-Silva et al. 2025). Currently, development with a higher degree of novelty for wound healing is continuously being developed (Ghaffari et al. 2018). However, commonly available semisolid dosage

forms have disadvantages, such as patient non-compliance because of frequent application 3–4 times a day. While nanotechnology developments are costly, complex, and time-consuming to scale up. Therefore, patch dosage form is an excellent solution to maintain patient compliance due to its sustained delivery process and higher contact time with the affected or wounded areas (Vicente-da-Silva et al. 2025). Furthermore, it is worth noting the patch's ability to act as a reservoir, which carries a higher number of active compounds based on polymer matrix entrapment capability (Miksusanti et al. 2020; Dong et al. 2024). One of the most used polymers for patch formulation is HPMC, owing to its robust features and flexible application (Suwandecha and Changklang 2023).

Herein, ethanolic extract from avocado leaves (ALEE) was obtained, which was characterized for phytochemical compounds. Patch formulation was then developed with various extract concentrations, with HPMC as the main polymer and additional components including plasticizer, PEG400, and propylene glycol. These patches were subjected to several evaluations, including homogeneity, folding endurance, and pH. An optimal formula was utilized for observing their wound healing ability in mice *in vivo* in a diabetic wound model. To confirm the molecular action of the phytochemicals contained in ALEE, *in silico* molecular docking was conducted to further trace the pathways involved in assisting diabetic wound treatment. The general scheme of the research can be seen in the graphical abstract below (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Graphical abstract and general scheme of research.

Material and methods

Materials

Avocado leaf extract (*Persea americana* Mill.) used in this study was purchased from the herbal medicine supplier PT. Rachma Sari Group, Indonesia. All reagents and solvents used were of analytical grade and purchased from Merck and Sigma-Aldrich. HPMC was purchased from Bratachem, Indonesia. Balb/C mice were procured from a certified laboratory animal provider in Yogyakarta.

Qualitative phytochemical screening assay

A phytochemical screening test was conducted to determine the presence of phytochemical compounds in the form of flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, and saponins in ALEE with qualitative analysis using methods following Warsi and Sholichah (2017) with modifications.

Flavonoid assay

A total of 0.5 grams of sample was weighed, then mixed with 5 mL of methanol and filtered. The filtrate was placed on filter paper and then evaporated using ammonia vapor. If the results obtained were in the form of an orange-yellow color, it showed the presence of a flavonoid compound.

Tannin assay

A total of 0.5 grams of extract was mixed with 5 mL of methanol, then filtered. The filtrate was then added to 1% FeCl₃. If the results obtained turned dark blue, it indicated tannin compounds present in the extract.

Alkaloid assay

A total of 0.5 grams of extract samples were mixed in 5 mL of 2 N HCl. After the previous treatment, the mixture was heated for 2 min, with temperature maintained using a water bath. Then the mixture was treated with Dragendorff reagent. The orange color or the presence of precipitate indicates the extract contains alkaloid compounds.

Saponin assay

A total of 0.5 grams of extract samples was added to 10 mL of hot water (~60 °C). After cooling, the mixture was shaken and added to one drop of 2 N HCl. The froth bubbles generated indicate the presence of saponin compounds.

Determination of total flavonoid content (TFC)

A total of 10 mg of quercetin was dissolved in ethanol p.a in a 10 mL volumetric flask to prepare a 1000 µg/mL stock solution. Five calibration levels were prepared at several concentrations to create calibration curve. Each solution (0.5 mL) was mixed with 0.1 mL of 10% AlCl₃, 1.5 mL ethanol, 0.1 mL 1 M sodium carbonate, and 2.8 mL dis-

tilled water. A total of 10 mg of ALEE was weighed and diluted 10 times with ethanol p.a. to a final volume of 5 mL to obtain sample mixtures. The mixtures were incubated at room temperature for 30 min and measured using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer at the maximum absorbance wavelength. A reagent blank containing all reagents except the sample extract was used to correct for background absorbance and potential matrix interference. Absorbance measurements were performed immediately after the incubation period to ensure consistent reaction development and solution stability during analysis. The flavonoid content (in mgQE/g extract) was calculated using the regression equation from the quercetin standard ($y = ax + b$), and total flavonoid content was calculated following Equation (1) below, with C (mg.mL⁻¹) as concentration, V as volume (mL), DF as dilution factor, and m as mass (g). Samples were repeated for analysis for reproducibility, with samples determined in three replicates of independent sample preparation. Relative standard deviation (RSD) was then calculated following Equation (2).

$$TFC \left(\frac{\text{mgQE}}{\text{g}_{\text{extract}}} \right) = \frac{C \times V \times DF}{m} \quad (1)$$

The parameter mgQE (milligram Quercetin Equivalent) represents the total flavonoid content expressed in terms of quercetin equivalents. The symbol C denotes the concentration of quercetin obtained from the calibration curve. V represents the total volume of the extract in milliliters (mL). DF refers to the dilution factor used during sample preparation. m indicates the mass of the sample in grams (g).

$$RSD = \frac{\text{standard deviation}}{\text{average}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Determination of total phenolic content (TPC)

Preparation of gallic acid stock solution started with a total of 12.5 mg of gallic acid dissolved in 0.5 mL ethanol p.a. and diluted to 25 mL with distilled water to obtain a stock solution (1000 µg/mL), in which five calibration levels were used to create a calibration curve. Separately, 10.6 g of sodium carbonate was dissolved in distilled water and diluted to 100 mL to prepare a 1 M Na₂CO₃ solution. The sample extract (10 mg) was also dissolved in 0.5 mL ethanol and diluted to 5 mL with distilled water to obtain the final solution. Determination of maximum wavelength (λ_{max}) was conducted with a 1 mL aliquot of gallic acid standard solution or sample mixed with 1 mL Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and 2 mL of 1 M Na₂CO₃ and added with ethanol until 5 mL. A reagent blank containing all reagents without a sample was prepared to correct background absorbance and minimize potential matrix interference. The mixture was incubated at room temperature for 30 min, and absorbance was measured at 766 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Absorbance measurements were performed immediately after incubation to ensure

analysis within the stable color development period. Total phenolic content was then calculated using Equation (3). The phenolic content in samples was determined in three replicates of independent measurements, and measurements were repeated on different days to observe reproducibility of results by measuring the RSD (Equation 2).

$$\text{TPC} \left(\frac{\text{mgGAE}}{\text{g}_{\text{extract}}} \right) = \frac{C \times V \times DF}{m} \quad (3)$$

The parameter mgGAE (milligram Gallic Acid Equivalent) represents the phenolic content calculated based on the gallic acid standard.

In silico assessment

Drug and disease target mapping

The Swiss Target Prediction analysis platform (swisstargetprediction.ch) was used to search for related protein targets. The Gene Cards platform (www.genecards.org/) was used to retrieve associated targets using the keywords “diabetic wound healing.” Intersecting targets of drugs and diseases were checked using a Venn diagram generated by the Bioinformatics & Evolutionary Genomics website (bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/webtools/Venn/), as seen in Fig. 2. The protein-protein interaction (PPI) network of the intersected drug-disease targets was created using the STRING and STITCH databases (string-db.org/; stitch-db.org/) with the minimum required interaction score of 0.400, and the topological parameters of the network were calculated using Cytoscape. The g:Profiler database ([/biit.cs.ut.ee/gprofiler/](http://biit.cs.ut.ee/gprofiler/)) was used to identify enriched gene ontology and KEGG pathways of the drug-disease intersection targets (Polat et al. 2020).

intersection

Figure 2. Ligand and disease target intersection.

Molecular docking

The AutoDock Vina platform in PyRx software was used to analyze the binding affinities and modes of interaction between the reference ligand, compounds, and their predicted targets. The PubChem database (pubchem.ncbi.

nlm.nih.gov/) was used to retrieve the molecular structure of all the ligands. The PDB website (rcsb.org) was used to download 3D targets with coordinates such as EGFR (PDB ID, 5HG7; resolution, 1.85 Å), PIK3-CA (PDB ID, 4JPS; resolution, 2.20 Å), erbB2 (PDB ID, 3PP0; resolution, 2.25 Å), MMP9 (PDB ID, 1L6J; resolution, 2.50 Å), and MMP2 (PDB ID, 1CK7; resolution, 2.80 Å). Polar hydrogen atoms were added to the protein target files, while water molecules were removed to transform them into the PDBQT format. Docking was performed using a grid box centered at the co-crystallized ligand binding site with the following coordinates and dimensions: EGFR center = (−3.6137, 18.9446, −21.7195), size = (42.8402, 47.2816, 59.2543); PIK3CA center = (−9.5558, −24.6441, 31.4699), size = (119.3254, 84.2747, 93.3243); and erbB2 center = (21.3912, 31.2543, 14.6846), size = (72.7786, 68.9064, 97.8152). The exhaustiveness parameter was set to 8, and 9 binding poses were generated for each ligand-protein complex, while all other parameters were kept at default settings.

To validate the docking protocol, re-docking was performed for each crystallographic complex using its respective native co-crystallized ligand: EGFR (PDB ID: 5HG7) with ligand 1-((3R,4R)-3-((5-chloro-2-((1-methyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)amino)-7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-yl)oxy)methyl)-4-methoxypyrrolidin-1-yl)propan-1-one, PIK3CA (PDB ID: 4JPS) with ligand (2S)-N~1~{4-methyl-5-[2-(1,1,1-trifluoro-2-methylpropan-2-yl)pyridin-4-yl]-1,3-thiazol-2-yl}pyrrolidine-1,2-dicarboxamide, and erbB2 (PDB ID: 3PP0) with ligand 2-{2-[4-(5-chloro-6-[3-(trifluoromethyl)phenoxy]pyridin-3-yl)amino]-5H-pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]ethoxy}ethanol. Each native ligand was extracted and re-docked into its original binding site using identical grid parameters.

The geometry-based root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) between the docked pose and the crystallographic ligand conformation was calculated using PyMOL 2.5 (<https://pymol.org/2/>), yielding an RMSD value of 0.958 Å for erbB2 (3PP0), 0.158 Å for PIK3-CA (4JPS), and 0.222 Å for EGFR (5HG7), which was considered acceptable when ≤ 2.0 Å. For metalloproteins such as MMP2 and MMP9, docking grids were centered on the catalytic Zn²⁺ ion to ensure appropriate sampling of the metalloprotein active site. Ligand poses were evaluated based on their proximity to the metal center and interactions with surrounding catalytic residues. A docking pose was considered plausible when ligand functional groups were positioned within a coordination distance of approximately 2.0–3.0 Å from the Zn²⁺ ion and simultaneously maintained stabilizing interactions with conserved residues within the catalytic pocket.

Ligand selection for docking was based on a multi-parameter prioritization strategy integrating ligand efficiency, predicted toxicity class, solubility, bioavailability score, and synthetic accessibility to ensure suitability for topical delivery. Compounds exhibiting favorable ligand efficiency (LE threshold ≤ -0.3 kcal/mol/heavy atom), acceptable toxicity profiles (toxicity class $\geq V$), adequate solubility, bioavailability scores ≥ 0.5 , and synthetic accessibility val-

ues below six were prioritized. Fumaric acid was excluded from further analysis due to the absence of overlapping targets with diabetic wound-healing-related pathways identified during network pharmacology analysis. Docking results were interpreted at a hypothesis-generating level, and predicted interactions were visualized using PyMOL 2.5 to analyze binding orientations, hydrogen bonding (H-bond distance ≤ 3.0 Å), and amino acid residues within the binding cavity that may contribute to ligand-target interactions relevant to wound healing-associated signaling pathways.

Preparation of ALEE patch

Patches were formulated by weighing the ingredients according to the composition shown in Table 1, following the method described by Mahajan et al. (2018) with modifications. Purified water was heated, and HPMC was allowed to swell in the heated purified water while stirring with a magnetic stirrer at 200 rpm for 10 mins. The ALEE was first dissolved in 70% ethanol and then slowly added to the HPMC solution. Methyl paraben, PEG 400, and propylene glycol were subsequently incorporated, and the mixture was stirred until a homogeneous solution was obtained. After homogenization, 3 g of the patch suspension was poured into the mold and dried in an oven at 50 °C for 3 h. The dried patches were then placed in a desiccator until further analysis.

Table 1. Formula of ALEE patch.

Component	F1 (%)	F2 (%)	F3 (%)
ALEE	5	10	15
HPMC	6	6	6
Propylene glycol	5	5	5
PEG 400	10	10	10
Methyl paraben	0.3	0.3	0.3
Ethanol 70%	30	30	30
Purified water	Ad 100	Ad 100	Ad 100

Physical characteristics evaluation of patch

Organoleptic tests were conducted to visually observe the appearance, color, and odor of the resulting patches. The weight uniformity test was carried out by weighing four patches from each formulation, followed by calculation of the standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CV). The pH test was conducted by immersing a patch in 10 mL of CO₂-free distilled water, followed by incubation at room temperature for 1 h. The pH of the resulting solution was then measured using a previously calibrated pH meter. The patch thickness test was carried out by randomly selecting patches from each formulation and measuring the thickness of the patch using a screw micrometer with 0.01 mm precision, after which the mean thickness for each formulation was calculated. The patch folding endurance test was performed by repeatedly fold-

ing a single patch at the same location until it broke or until 300 manual folds were reached, as described by Miksusanti et al. (2020).

Experimental animal preparation

A total of 18 *Mus musculus* type Balb/C were acclimatized to the new environment prior to testing for 1 week. Previously, this study had received approval from the ethics committee to use test animals as research subjects by the Ahmad Dahlan University Research Ethics Committee with Number: 012407182. The animals were randomly divided into six groups using a random-number generator, with three animals in each group (Table 2). All groups of mice were rendered hyperglycemic except for the normal control group, followed by wound induction in all test animals. Treatments were administered, and the wound healing process was observed for 14 days.

Wound healing activity of ALEE in an alloxan-induced diabetic mouse

The wound healing assay was conducted using an alloxan-induced diabetic mouse model. Hyperglycemia was induced by administration of alloxan, and the diabetic condition was confirmed by measuring blood glucose levels. Wound healing activity was evaluated by comparing the effectiveness of treatment groups receiving the formulated patches with control groups. The rate of wound closure was assessed by measuring the wound diameter over the observation period.

Induction of hyperglycemia in experimental animals

All mice were fasted for 16 h prior to induction, after which baseline blood glucose levels were measured. Mice in groups 2 to 6 were subcutaneously injected with alloxan (120 mg/kgBB) dissolved in 0.9% NaCl solution to induce hyperglycemia. Blood glucose levels were remeasured 24–48 h after alloxan administration to confirm the hyperglycemic condition (Matusin et al. 2021). Blood samples were obtained from the tail vein after sterilization with 70% ethanol, and glucose levels were determined using a portable glucometer (Elzwi and Alabdali 2024). Measurements were performed twice (before and after alloxan administration) to confirm successful induction of hyperglycemia.

Incision wounds on experimental animals

Wound creation was performed after confirmation of hyperglycemia. Mice were randomized and anesthetized with ketamine HCl (80 mg/kgBB). Adequate anesthesia was confirmed using the toe-pinch reflex. The dorsal hair was shaved to expose the skin, and the area was disinfected with 70% ethanol. A full-thickness circular wound (5 mm diameter) was then created using a biopsy punch. Immediately after wound creation, mice received treatment according to their respective groups. The wound area was subsequently covered with sterile gauze and medical plaster to minimize contamination (Wijaya et al. 2020; Hanbisa et al. 2023).

Table 2. Experimental groups.

Group number	Group	Hyperglycemic status	Wound treatment
1	Normal control	Non Hyperglycemic mice	Only wounded
2	Negative control	Hyperglycemic mice	Patch base once a day
3	Positive control	Hyperglycemic mice	Bioplacenton once a day
4	Treatment F1	Hyperglycemic mice	Patch F1 is applied once a day.
5	Treatment F2	Hyperglycemic mice	Patch F2 is applied once a day.
6	Treatment F3	Hyperglycemic mice	Patch F3 is applied once a day.

Observations on treated experimental animals

Treatment given for each group is presented in Table 2. Wound healing activity was evaluated by monitoring wound diameter and qualitative wound characteristics throughout the observation period. Baseline wound diameter (day 0) was recorded prior to treatment, and subsequent measurements were conducted on days 3, 5, 7, 10, 12, and 14. Wound diameter was measured using a digital caliper, with four measurements taken in different directions for each wound and averaged for analysis.

Qualitative wound observations were also performed based on redness, edema, wound dryness, scab formation, and the presence of pus, which were assessed using a scoring system adapted from Widyaningsih et al. (2022) (Table 3). Wound scoring was conducted on days 7 and 14, representing key stages of the healing process, namely the proliferative phase and the transition toward the remodeling phase.

Statistical analysis

Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Prior to statistical analysis, data were assessed for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test and for homogeneity of variance using Levene's test. When the assumptions of normality and homogeneity were satisfied, differences among groups were analyzed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's p post-hoc test for multiple comparisons. When the data were not normally distributed, non-parametric analysis was performed using the Kruskal-Wallis test followed by the Mann-Whitney test with Bonferroni correction to evaluate differences in wound diameter among all experimental groups, in which each group was compared pairwise with one another. Statistical analysis was conducted using GraphPad Prism 9 and SPSS 31, with the level of statistical significance (*) defined as $p < 0.05$, (**) defined as $p < 0.01$, and (***) defined as $p < 0.001$.

Results and discussion

Result of qualitative and quantitative phytochemical screening

Phytochemical screening of ALEE confirmed the presence of flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, and saponins (Fig. 3A–D). The flavonoid assay yielded an orange–yellow

coloration on the filter paper, indicating a positive result. Tannins were identified by the development of a dark blue coloration. The alkaloid test demonstrated the formation of a precipitate, confirming their presence in the extract. Furthermore, the saponin assay produced stable foam, consistent with a positive indication of saponins (Khalisha and Arsianti 2024). The calibration curves for total flavonoid content (TFC) and total phenolic content (TPC) are presented in Fig. 3E, F, with regression equations of $y = 0.0185x + 0.0166$ and $y = 0.006838x + 0.03568$, respectively. Both curves exhibited excellent linearity, as indicated by correlation coefficients (R^2) exceeding 0.99. Quantitative analysis revealed that the extract contained 274.08 mg GAE/g of phenolic compounds and 125.78 mg QE/g of flavonoids (Fig. 3G–H). The reproducibility of the TPC and TFC assays was assessed through inter-day analysis, with all relative standard deviation (RSD) values below 5%, demonstrating good method precision and consistency across different days.

Preparation of ALEE patch

Topical drug delivery systems provide localized drug administration to the skin by enabling prolonged contact time and potentially improving drug availability at the target site. Patch-based preparations were selected because they can reduce dosing frequency and allow convenient application to the wound area. HPMC, as the primary component of the patch matrix, functions as a film-forming agent (Jaber 2023). Due to its hydrophilic nature, HPMC can absorb moisture and facilitate drug diffusion from the polymeric matrix, thereby promoting release at the localized site of application. Additionally, propylene glycol was incorporated as a plasticizer to maintain the flexibility of the patch and prevent brittleness during application (Fitrya et al. 2021).

Physical characteristics evaluation of patch

The ALEE patch dosage had a green color, a slightly rough texture, and a distinctive odor. The color intensity increased with the concentration of ALEE (Fig. 4). The weight uniformity increased with increasing extract concentration, and significant differences were found between formulas ($p < 0.05$). The weight uniformity test could be analyzed using the CV value. The test results showed that the dosage was uniform when the CV value was less than 5%.

Table 3. Wound scoring with parameters of redness, edema, wound dryness, scab formation, and pus.

Score	Redness	Edema	Wound dryness	Scab	Pus
0	None	None	Fully dry	None	None
1	Slight (1–30%)	Slight (1–30%)	Mostly dry (31–70%)	Thin (31–70%)	Slight (1–30%)
2	Moderate (31–70%)	Moderate (31–70%)	Partially dry (1–30%)	Thick (1–30%)	Moderate (31–70%)
3	Severe (71–100%)	Severe (71–100%)	Not dry/Wet (71–100%)	Very thick (31–70%)	Abundant (71–100%)

Figure 4. Organoleptic test results of A. 5% concentration; B. 10% concentration; C. 15% concentration; D. Patch attached to hepafix.

All three formulations demonstrated folding endurance values greater than 300 folds, indicating that the patches possessed sufficient mechanical strength and would not easily break during application to the skin. However, a slight decrease in folding endurance was observed with increasing extract concentration (Suwandecha and Changklang 2023). The pH test was performed to evaluate the compatibility of the patch formulation with the physiological pH of the skin. An acceptable pH range for topical preparations is typically between 4.5 and 6.5 to minimize the risk of skin irritation. Based on

Table 4, all formulas fulfilled the pH requirements in the range of 4.5–6.5.

The thickness of the patches increased with increasing extract concentrations. Significant differences were observed among the formulations ($p < 0.05$), which were directly proportional to the corresponding patch weights. An ideal patch should possess minimal thickness while maintaining adequate mechanical strength to prevent tearing during application. Based on Table 4, all formulations met the acceptable thickness requirement, with values below 1 mm (Miksusanti et al. 2020).

Table 4. Physical characteristics evaluation of patch.

No	Evaluation	Requirement	Result of formula (mean \pm SD; $n = 3$)		
			F1 (5%)	F2 (10%)	F3 (15%)
1.	Organoleptic	Green color, characteristic aroma of leaf avocado extract, round, thin, smooth, and elastic	Green color, characteristic aroma of leaf avocado extract, round, thin, smooth, and elastic	Green color, characteristic aroma of leaf avocado extract, round, thin, smooth, and elastic	Green color, characteristic aroma of leaf avocado extract, round, thin, smooth, and elastic
2.	Weight (grams)	–	1.45 \pm 0.04**	1.55 \pm 0.02**	1.76 \pm 0.04**
3.	Weight Uniformity/CV (%)	CV < 5%	2.77%	1.29%	2.28%
4.	Thickness (mm)	< 1 mm	0.44 \pm 0.04**	0.62 \pm 0.03**	0.75 \pm 0.02**
5.	pH	4.5–6.5	5.45 \pm 0.03**	5.73 \pm 0.04**	5.88 \pm 0.10**
6.	Folding endurance (times)	> 300 times	322.3 \pm 4.51**	336.6 \pm 4.51**	304.6 \pm 2.52**

** = $p < 0.01$

In silico assessment

Network pharmacology and molecular docking are often used in drug research, discovery, and development. In this study, 171 drug-related targets of avocado leaf ethanolic extract and 4879 diabetic wound disease-related targets were detected. The related targets were intersected and were shown to have 123 drug–disease intersected targets. To investigate the protein–protein interactions, protein–compound interactions, and potential mechanism of the compound action for diabetic wound treatment, a PPI network was constructed and was shown to have high combined scores for AKT1, MMP9, EGFR, ESRI, SRC, BCL2L1, TNF, MMP2, ERBB2, and MCL1, indicating that the compounds could act upon their medicinal effects through multiple targets, as shown in Fig. 5. The GO enrichment assay suggested that the compounds might impact protein kinase activity, regulation of apoptotic processes, cellular metabolic regulation, and regulation of miRNA transcription and cellular component organization. The KEGG pathway assay suggested that the compounds might regulate angiogenesis, matrix metalloproteinase, PI3K–Akt, EGFR, and AGE–RAGE signaling pathways in diabetic complications. These pathways are linked to metabolic, inflammatory, proliferative, and immunological responses, which implies that the compounds' therapeutic benefits on diabetic wounds are likewise linked to these reactions.

Molecular docking analysis was performed to assess the binding affinities of each compound for targets. The Autodock Vina v.1.5.6 in PyRx software pinpointed and determined the binding sites, the interactions, and the binding energy was determined. From 17 compounds, only 5 were chosen to be visualized and identified based on ligand efficiency, ADMET, LD50, and bioavailability. From the result, the highest binding affinity for each receptor with the chosen compound was obtained, as seen in Table 5.

To validate the docking protocol, re-docking was conducted by extracting the native ligand from representative protein structures and re-docking it into the original binding site using identical grid parameters (Mardiyanto et al. 2026). The geometry-based root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) between the docked pose and the crystallograph-

ic ligand conformation was calculated using PyMOL 2.5 (<https://pymol.org/2/>), yielding an RMSD value of 0.958 Å for erbB2 (3PP0), 0.158 Å for PIK3-CA (4JPS), and 0.222 Å for EGFR (5HG7), which was considered acceptable when ≤ 2.0 Å. For metalloproteins such as MMP2 and MMP9, docking grids were centered on the catalytic Zn²⁺ ion, and ligand interactions were evaluated based on proximity to the metal center and surrounding active site residues.

Wound healing activity of ALEE patch in an alloxan-induced diabetic mouse

Blood sugar results of mice after induction

All groups of mice, except the healthy control group, were injected with alloxan, a diabetogenic compound known to selectively damage pancreatic β -cells, thereby reducing insulin production. Prior to administration, alloxan powder was dissolved in physiological saline (0.9% NaCl). Alloxan is widely used to induce experimental diabetes because it generates reactive oxygen species that cause oxidative damage to insulin-producing pancreatic β -cells (Matusin et al. 2021; Elzwi and Alabdali 2024). Within 24–72 h after administration, alloxan disrupts hepatic glycogen metabolism and further damages pancreatic cells through free radical formation, ultimately leading to decreased insulin secretion (Alshaer et al. 2022). Twenty-four hours after alloxan induction, blood glucose levels of the experimental animals were measured again to confirm the establishment of hyperglycemic conditions. Blood glucose levels in mice were determined after a 12-h fasting period using a glucometer. The blood glucose data obtained from the mice are presented in Table 6. A significant increase in blood glucose levels was observed after alloxan administration compared with pre-induction values (Fig. 8A).

Result of wound healing effectiveness test

Based on macroscopic observations, the wound condition was qualitatively evaluated using several parameters that reflect different stages of the wound healing process. During the inflammatory phase, wounds typically exhibit pronounced redness and edema as part of the body's initial inflammatory response (Azadi et al. 2011). At this

Figure 5. Result of relevant target **A.** STRING result and **B.** STITCH result.

Table 5. Amino acid residues and binding affinity of compounds in receptors.

Compound	Receptor	Binding affinity	Amino acid residue
Apigenin	5HG7 (EGFR)	-8.4	GLN-791, MET-793
	4JPS (PIK3-CA)	-7.8	ARG-852, HIS-759, ASN-797
	3PP0 (erbB2)	-8.9	LYS-753, ALA-751
	1L6J (MMP9)	-7.9	LYS-578, VAL-620
	1CK7 (MMP2)	-8.5	THR-96, GLY-186, ASP-185
Caffeic acid	5HG7 (EGFR)	-6.1	GLN-791, MET-793
	4JPS (PIK3-CA)	-6.3	PRO-835, SER-629
	3PP0 (erbB2)	-7.1	GLN-415
	1L6J (MMP9)	-7.8	GLU-402
	1CK7 (MMP2)	-6.9	LEU-796
Ellagic acid	5HG7 (EGFR)	-8	LEU-718, MET-793
	4JPS (PIK3-CA)	-9.1	ASN-428, GLN-643, ARG-683, GLN-682, THR-679
	3PP0 (erbB2)	-9	ASN-55, TYR-182, ASN-111
	1L6J (MMP9)	-8.7	TYR-52, ARG-51, GLU-47
	1CK7 (MMP2)	-9.1	ASP-863, LYS-753, MET-801
Gallic acid	5HG7 (EGFR)	-6	ASP-855, LEU-777, MET-766
	4JPS (PIK3-CA)	-5.8	ASP-538, ASN-996, ALA-995
	3PP0 (erbB2)	-7	ASN-573, ASP-622, GLU-525, ILE-481, GLN-480
	1L6J (MMP9)	-7.1	THR-426, ARG-424, TYR-420, LEU-418
	1CK7 (MMP2)	-6.7	GLU-770
Quercetin	5HG7 (EGFR)	-8.2	LEU-718, GLN-791
	4JPS (PIK3-CA)	-7.5	GLU-821, ARG-818, GLN-630
	3PP0 (erbB2)	-9.4	LYS-578, ASN-573, ASP-622
	1L6J (MMP9)	-9.3	PRO-421, PRO-430
	1CK7 (MMP2)	-8.9	ASP-863, LYS-753

Table 6. Blood sugar level results.

	Blood sugar level results (mg/dL \pm SD ($n = 3$))					
	Healthy group	Negative control	Positive control	F1 (5%)	F2 (10%)	F3 (15%)
Before alloxan induction	116 \pm 12.96	120 \pm 0.82	119.67 \pm 18.35	117.33 \pm 4.64	119 \pm 6.53	119 \pm 12.25
After alloxan induction	-	470 \pm 139.18	396.33 \pm 97.91	600 \pm 0	547.67 \pm 74.01	474.33 \pm 177.72

Figure 6. Docking result with the highest ligand efficiency A. Gallic acid in 5HG7; B. Caffeic acid in 4JPS; C. Gallic acid in 3PP0; D. Caffeic acid in 1L6J; E. Gallic acid in 1CK7.

Figure 7. Pathway of A. PI3K–AKT signaling; B. ErbB2 signaling; C. MMP signaling, and D. MAPK/ERK signaling.

stage, the wound surface generally remains moist and may show signs of exudate or infection. During the proliferation phase, redness and edema gradually decrease, the wound begins to dry, and scab formation occurs. In the remodeling phase, the wound becomes drier and signs of inflammation further diminish, while the scab gradually

detaches as tissue regeneration progresses (Andritoiu et al. 2021). The wound healing progress in the six experimental groups was assessed using a qualitative scoring system based on wound appearance. After macroscopic observation, scores were assigned to each group according to the defined scoring criteria. Scoring was performed

Figure 8. Graphic of A. Blood sugar level observed between before and after alloxan induction; B. Scoring value of treatment compared to controls on different days, and C. Diameter of diabetic wound observed on different days (ns = not significant; * = $p < 0.05$).

on days 7 and 14 (Fig. 8B), as these time points represent the proliferative phase and the transition toward the remodeling phase of wound healing. Based on the wound assessment data presented in Table 7, the results of the normality test indicated that the data were not normally distributed. Therefore, Kruskal–Wallis was used to analyze data, in which the analysis results showed a statistically significant difference between the wound scores on day 7 and day 14 ($p < 0.05$). The post-hoc pairwise comparison with Mann–Whitney using Bonferroni correction exhibited significant differences, indicating a notable progression in the wound healing process over time.

Table 7. Data of total mean \pm SD scoring values in each treatment group.

Treatment group	Mean \pm SD ($n = 3$)	
	Day 7	Day 14
Healthy group	1.60 \pm 0.00	0.20 \pm 0.00
Positive control	1.80 \pm 0.00	0.40 \pm 0.00
Negative control	2.60 \pm 0.28	2.17 \pm 0.12
Treatment F1	1.87 \pm 0.00	0.80 \pm 0.00
Treatment F2	2.00 \pm 0.00	0.60 \pm 0.00
Treatment F3	1.80 \pm 0.00	0.60 \pm 0.00

Following macroscopic evaluation using wound assessment parameters, the reduction in wound diameter was measured quantitatively. The mean \pm SD of the reduction in wound diameter on the rat's back after treatment is presented in Fig. 8C. Based on Table 8 and Fig. 8, a reduction in wound diameter was observed in all treatment groups, and statistical analysis was performed separately on days

0, 3, 5, 7, 10, 12, and 14 across groups. Normality test results indicated that the data on all days were not normally distributed ($p < 0.05$); therefore, the analysis continued using the Kruskal–Wallis test with Mann–Whitney using Bonferroni correction. The results showed no significant differences between groups at those time points; this was due to the small sample size of test animals in each group, resulting in high biological variation that significantly affected the statistical analysis. Although the statistical results did not show significant differences, the trend in the figures indicates that the wounds narrowed, with a diameter from 5 mm to approximately ± 1 mm in every group, except in the patch base group (negative control).

In an attempt to explain the observed wound healing activity, there have been previous reports explaining the mechanism of phytochemical compounds such as saponin, alkaloid, and flavonoid toward wound healing. Flavonoids have shown to manipulate multiple pathways relating to wound healing, including transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β), c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK), nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B), nitric oxide (NO), MAPK/ERK, phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3K)/Akt, and Ras/Raf/MEK/ERK pathways (Zulkefli et al. 2023). These pathways are essential during the inflammation and proliferation steps, hence impacting the wound healing process. Additionally, alkaloids have demonstrated matrix organization and collagenation with saponin along with fibroblast proliferation, while saponin has shown excellent collagen deposition during wound healing (Kim et al. 2011; Mahibalan et al. 2016). Based on these explanations, these mechanisms may partly explain the wound healing activity observed for the ALEE patch formulation in the present study.

Table 8. Anatomical observation and wound diameter results of experimental animals.

Treatment group	Macroscopic wound diameter on different days (mm) (mean \pm SD, $n = 3$)						
	Day 0	Day 3	Day 5	Day 7	Day 10	Day 12	Day 14
Healthy group							
	5.13 \pm 0.05	3.5 \pm 1.15	3.07 \pm 0.78	3.13 \pm 0.46	1.63 \pm 0.42	1.20 \pm 0.08	1.03 \pm 0.05
Positive control							
	5.03 \pm 0.05	3.53 \pm 0.69	3.17 \pm 0.87	2.30 \pm 0.08	2.23 \pm 0.37	1.50 \pm 0.50	1.07 \pm 0.05
Negative control							
	5.23 \pm 0.33	6.50 \pm 1.82	6.00 \pm 1.56	4.53 \pm 0.90	5.37 \pm 2.25	3.90 \pm 0.92	3.70 \pm 1.04
Treatment F1							
	5.17 \pm 0.09	4.20 \pm 0.59	3.47 \pm 0.82	3.13 \pm 0.34	2.53 \pm 0.26	1.27 \pm 0.05	1.07 \pm 0.05
Treatment F2							
	5.07 \pm 0.05	4.80 \pm 0.51	4.20 \pm 0.75	3.37 \pm 0.37	3.03 \pm 0.54	1.83 \pm 0.89	1.57 \pm 0.73
Treatment F3							
	5.13 \pm 0.05	4.30 \pm 0.42	3.70 \pm 0.59	3.07 \pm 0.54	2.17 \pm 0.78	1.57 \pm 0.59	1.37 \pm 0.52

Conclusion

Variations in the concentration of ALEE affected the physical properties of the patches, including color, pH, weight uniformity, thickness, and folding endurance. Among the tested formulations, Formula 2 containing 10% ALEE exhibited the most favorable physical characteristics, with weight uniformity (CV) of 1.29%, pH 5.73 ± 0.04 , thickness 0.62 ± 0.03 mm, and folding endurance of 336.6 ± 4.51 folds. Based on the *in silico* evaluation, phytochemical compounds identified in avocado leaf extract, including apigenin, gallic acid, and caffeic acid, showed relatively strong predicted binding affinities toward receptors associated with wound healing pathways. The ALEE patches at concentrations of 5%, 10%, and 15% demonstrated diabetic wound healing activity in mice, as indicated by the reduction in wound diameter of 5 mm to approximately ± 1 mm. The activity was not statistically different from the Bioplacenton positive control under the tested conditions, suggesting a potentially beneficial effect of the ALEE patch formulation on the wound healing process.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: Ahmad Dahlan University Research Ethics Committee with Number: 012407182.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Author contributions

Citra Ariani Edityaningrum – principal investigator, conceived the presented idea, planned the experiments, monitored and evaluated data generation.

Laela Hayu Nuraini and Wahyu Widyaningsih – provide assist with the data gathering and evaluation.

Baiq Shanaya Zaelifa, Fivdah Khoeruliani Tazqiyah, Revi Adelia, Cintana Violena Alifia Putri, Daffa Danurwenda – conducted the research and obtained the data.

Farah Daffa Azzahra, Siti Humairoh, Rumiayati Dwi Nindi – in silico evaluation and data gathering, statistical evaluation.

Najma Annuria Fithri – editing of manuscript, proofreading and monitoring of in silico results and interpretation.

Author ORCIDs

Citra Ariani Edityaningrum <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4113-6233>

Najma Annuria Fithri <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0311-8170>

Laela Hayu Nurani <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3327-0624>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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